

Documentary Appendix

“‘Translatio reliquiae’ and ‘translatio imperii’ between Italy and north-eastern Europe in the Age of Partition (c. 1750-1800): the case of the Plater in Polish Livonia.”

In: *The Migration of Artists and Architects in Central and Northern Europe, 1560–1900.*

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Appendix 1.

Letter from Filippo Castaldi to Kazimierz Konstanty Plater, 22 January 1774. Vilnius, Lithuanian State Historical Archives, coll. 1276, reg. 2, 123, ff 64r-65v (no. 45).

Transcription of original text

J'ay l'honneur d'assurer Votre Excellence de mon profond respect, et du souvenir perpetuele, que j'ay, malgré l'enorme distance , qui nous separe, de votre très digne Personne, et de vos bienfaits, don't je n'en pourrai jamais m'oublier.

J'ose dans le meme sens vous exposer, comme ayant prises toutes mesures necessaires, et toutes connaissances les plus utiles pour venir à bout d'obtenir de Notre St. Pere un coprs particulier de quelque Saint: et depuis d'avoir ainsi eu toutes les meilleurs assurances, je viens d'appndre, qu'à cause d'avoir pour bien deux fois inutilement cherché de les trouver dans les catacombs selon la coutume, et le temps fixé, il faut absolument à present en obtenir un rescrit¹ gracieux de Notre S. Pere, à fin, que je puisse en avoir un de ceux, qui sont reserves à la seule disposition du meme Souvrain Pontife: et meme pour en avoir un en meilleure forme, et de quelque meilleure consideration; et que pour obtenir ce rescrit soit mieux, que moi meme je me presente à ses pieds pour en faire la supplique. Vraiment on m'a persuade beaucoup d'executer ce project-là, mais comme je na'y n'en de que monstrier pour mieux convalider l'instance au nom de Monseigneur Votre Pere (à qui je m'humilie) ainsi je voue prie de vouloir bien vous charger de m'envoyer une requete telle, quelle vous la voyez ci renfermée; et de la faire signer par Monseigneur Votre Pere de sa proper main, et la fermer de son sceau. Vous aurez aussi Monseigneur, la bonté d'y ajouter une lettre ostensible par la quelle vous, ou soit Monseigneur Votre Pere, me mande à peu pres ces memes mots = depuis, Monsieur que il est necessaire pour obtenir le Corps Saint en question que vous vous presentiez à notre St. Pere

¹ On this term see below.

pour le prier de ma part de vouloir m'accorder cette grace, je vous envoie ici-jointe ma requete, que vous aurez soin de lui humilier tout au plus tôt de ma part, et de le prier que et devoir charger que il ne sera, que mieux, Monseigneur, si cette lettre, que vous me ferez avoir en response on l'aura faite en Latin.

Vous recevrez par ce meme courier deux autres petits enveloppes qui renferment deux reliques, une de la vbraie Croix pour son Excellence Madame Votre Epouse, et l'autre de St. Louis Roi de France pour Monseigneur votre Pere. Je vous prie de les accepter comme un petit attestat de mon sincere respect, et de ma vive reconnaissance, avec quelle j'ay l'honneur d'etre à jamais Monseigneur de Votre Excellence.

Rome le 22 Janvier 1774

Votre très humble, et très obeyissant serviteur

Philippe Castaldi

Translation

His Excellency My Lord Count Kazimierz [Konstanty] Plater, Starost of Dyneburg [today Daugavpils, Latvia],

I have the honor to assure Your Excellence of my profound respect, and of the perpetual memory that I hold, despite the enormous distance separating us, for your very worthy Person, and for your many graces, which I could never forget.

For this at the same time I dare to explain to you, having taken all the necessary measures and made all useful introductions to the end of obtaining from Our Holy Father Pope Clement XIV the body of some Saint, and having had to this end all the best assurances, I have come to find out—having gone already twice in vain to find whole body relics in the catacombs according

to established custom and practice—it is now absolutely necessary to obtain a *Rescript*² from Our Holy Father so that I might have one of these relics, which are the sole purview of the same Sovereign Pontiff. And to even have relics in better condition, and of better consideration, and to improve the chances to obtain this *Rescript*, I should present myself personally at the Pope's feet to make the entreaty.

Truly I have been greatly persuaded to commence this undertaking, but as I have nothing to show in order to better validate the petition on behalf of Konstanty Ludwik Plater (to whom I humbly address myself) thus I pray that you might be so kind as to send to me such a request, which you will find enclosed herein. And that you may have it signed by My Lord Your Father in his own hand and closed with his own seal. You might also have the goodness, My Lord, to add to this a letter in which you or My Lord Your Father writes to me more or less these same words: "Since Monsieur Castaldi, in order to obtain the Holy Relics in question, it is necessary that you present yourself to our Holy Father the Pope to entreat on my behalf to consent this to me this grace, I send here attached my request, which you will take care to humbly convey to the Pope as soon as possible on my behalf..." ...and to make this supplication it would be better, My Lord, that this letter which you will write to me in reply should be in Latin.

You will receive with this same letter delivery two other small envelopes which enclose two relics, one of the true Cross for her Excellence My Lady Your Wife,³ and the other of St. Louis King of France for My Lord your Father. I pray that you will accept them as a small testimony proof witness of my sincere respect, and of my deepest gratitude, with which I have the honor to hold forever for My Lord Your Excellency.

² The papal rescript (Latin re-scribere, "to write back") mentioned in Castaldi's letter signified in canon law the written response of the pope or a Sacred Congregation to individual queries or petitions. Administratively rescripts cut a wide swath, concerning the granting of favors or administration of justice, e.g. a legal opinion or judicial appointment. On the history and functions of the rescript see Meehan, Andrew. "Papal Rescripts." *The Catholic Encyclopedia* (1911), <http://www.newadvent.org/cathen/12783b.htm> (accessed 1 May 2021); William H. O'Neill, *Papal Rescripts of Favor*. Washington: Catholic University of America Press, 1930, 65-67.

³ Izabela Ludwika Plater née Borch (1752–1813).

Rome 22 January 1774. Your most humble and obedient servant, Filippo Castaldi.

Appendix 2.

Letter from Francesco Paracca (Castello Vlasolda, Italy) to Kazimierz Plater (Krāslava), 15 February 1770. Vilnius, LSHA, coll. 1276, reg. 2, file 119, ff. 72r-73v.

Transcription of original text

Eccellenza

Essendo infinite le obligationi che professo d'aveva coll'eccellenza sua, mancarci perciò al dover mio qual or non la reguagliarsi del mio felice arivo in Italia. Qui giunto non ho mancato giusto le ordini che l'eccellemtissimo Suo Sig. Padre sia degnato di mi ponersi di recercar gli operari che desiderava, ma impossibile mi riesce il render la servita adeso che niuno a rischiar si vole á venir in Polonia a cagione dele guerre che sconvolge ora questo Regno anzi se io stesso non avessi costi le fabbriche di già cominciate, avrei dei buoni riguardi á ritornarvi, ciò nonostante però accetar si deve della mia inalterabile servitù, è che in ogni unione suo mi preggio di a piegarmi á di lei comandi qual or me ne faccia degno, in tanto con tutto l'ossequio puo testandomi mi di havro dell'Eccellenza Sua Divotissimo et Obligatissimo Servo.

Francesco Parocco [sic]

Castello [Valsolda] li 15 Feb. 1770

Translation

Your Excellence (Kazimierz Plater)

Because the obligations and duties that I have for Your excellency are infinite, for this reason I have failed in my duty to notify you of my happy arrival in Italy. After I have come (to Italy) I have not failed in the orders that the most excellent Sir Your Father [Konstanty Ludwik Plater] so nobly gave to me, that is to search out the artisans that he wanted. But it is impossible to succeed in this service, now that nobody wants to risk coming to Poland due to the wars that tear apart this kingdom. Furthermore, if I myself did not already have some building projects begun and under way there [in Poland-Lithuania], I would worry myself about going back there. All this notwithstanding, please accept my unflinching servitude, that in everything You deign to command me, I undertake myself with the greatest effort. With all obsequies I remain your most humble servant.

Francesco Parocca

Appendix 3.

Letter from Domenico Paracca (Krāslava) to Kazimierz Plater (Warsaw), 11 November 1766. Vilnius, LSHA, coll. 1276, reg. 2, file 116, 90.

Transcription of original text

Eccellentissimo Signore Mio Prontissimo Colissimo

Avendo inteso che la Signora Palatina di Minsk si ritrova a Varsavia et ricordandomi della promessa di Vostra Eccellenza vengo a supplicarlo di volersi degnare di persuadere la sudetta con dirli che [...?] una chiesa grande et un Idem spaziale et difficile [sic] a edificare, li invio il disegno cioè la pianta la quale spero che la vedrà anche Vostra Signore novità di questo paese altro non li posso notificarli solo che la settimana ventura spero di terminare il tetto del palazzo

il quale la metà è di già terminato et coperto; et per non interrompere lo suoi studii resto Vostra Eccellenza Umilissimo Servo D[omenico] Paraka [sic]. Kraslavia [sic] li 11 Novembre 1766.

Translation

My Most Excellent Lord

Having learned that Her Ladyship Palatine of Minsk⁴ is in Warsaw, and remembering Your Excellency's promise to me, I am writing to beg of you that you might deign to persuade Her Ladyship by telling her that [...] a large and spacious [tall and wide] church difficult to build, I am sending to her a drawing, that is the [church] plan, which I hope also Your Lordship will recognize as an innovation in this territory. Besides this, I can only notify her that by the next week I hope to have completed the roof of the palace, which is already half finished and covered. So as not to further disturb your studies I remain Your Excellency's Most Humble Servant, Domenico Paracca. Krāslava, 11 November 1766.

Appendix 4.

Excerpt from testament of Augusta Plater née Ogińska (1724-91) of 28 November 1789, in which she bequeaths certain funds to finish the chapel of St. Donatus and crypt in Krāslava (Pol. Krasław), in present-day Latvia.⁵

Transcription of original text

Mając zaś w intencji do kościoła krasławskiego, przez Ich miłość XX Zgromadzenia reguły świętego Wincentego a Paulo zarządzanego, dla świętego Donata z Rzymu sprowadzonego

⁴ Referring to Konstancja Plater (1720-?), wife of Jan August Hylzen (or Hülsen von Eckeln, 1702-1767).

⁵ Riga, Latvian State Historical Archive, 712.f, 1.apr., 125.l. Sincere thanks to Reinis Norkārklis for assistance in accessing this material. Regarding conventions for modernizing Polish spelling, which has been applied in this and certain other Appendices texts, see Kazimierz Lepszy, ed., *Instrukcja wydawnicza dla źródeł historycznych : od XVI do połowy XIX wieku*. Wrocław: Zakład im. Ossolińskich, 1953.

widzieć domurowaną kaplicę, a pod nią grób wystawiony dla ciał zmarłych męża mojego i mnie samej i familii naszej, do czego z postanowienia z Ich miłością Xdzem proboszczem krasławskim, przedsiębiorącym takowe murowanie, wzięłam na siebie opłatę rzemieślnika, przeto jeżeliby nie skończywszy, a tym bardziej nie zacząwszy takowej wspólnie z Ich [m[iłości]ę Xdzem fabryki zejść mnie przyszło, zlecam uskutecznienie synowi mojemu Augustowi, kasztelanowemu trockiemu, i wielce obowiązuję, aby z sum od niego mnie należących oddzieliwszy 16000 Złotych Pollskich użył ich i czym rychlej pomienioną ze sklepem wymurować starał się z Ich miłością Xdzem proboszczem krasławskim kaplicę. A jeżeliby sama rzeczona fabrykę dokończyła, nie odmieniwszy w tej mierze dyspozycji niniejszej, tedy z rzeczonych 16000 Złotych Pollskich syn mój August 4000 Złotych Pollskich do rąk zwierzchności należnej Zgromadzenia Ich miłością XX. reguły świętego Wincentego a Paulo domu krasławskiego wypłaci na fundusz lampy dzień i noc palić się powinnej w kaplicy świętego Donata, osobny na to biorąc dokument z ubezpieczeniem jak najwarowniejszym, a 1200 Złotych Pollskich do massy wejdą sum poniżej rozdysponowanych...

Translation

Having the intention to see to the church in Krāslava, managed by the reverend priests of the Congregation of the rule of saint Vincent de Paul [Lazarists, Missionaries, or Congregation of the Mission],⁶ for saint Donatus brought from Rome, a chapel added and under it a crypt built for the bodies of the deceased my husband and myself and our family, to this [project] decided with reverend Krāslava parish priest who undertakes such masonry, I took for myself [the responsibility for] the payment of an artisan, so if without finishing it, or even without beginning this project with the reverend priest, I would die, I commission the realization to my

⁶ On the Plater's patronage of Catholic religious orders in Krāslava, see Joanna Orzeł and Stanisław Roszak, "Letters of Piotr Hiacynt Śliwicki to the Papal Nuncio Alberico Archinto from the Years 1754–1757 in the Collections of the Vatican Archive," *Zapiski Historyczne* lxxxiii, no. 1 (2018):175-192.

son August,⁷ son of the castellan of Trakai [Troki],⁸ and oblige him greatly that he from the sum that he owes me, having separated 16 000 Polish Zloty, would use them and erect as soon as possible the aforementioned chapel with a crypt together with the reverend Krāslava parish priest. As if I would have finished this project by myself, without having changed this disposition, in that case from the sum of 16 000 Polish Zloty my son August would pay 4 000 Polish Zloty to the hands of the elders of the reverend Congregation of the rule of saint Vincent de Paul house in Krāslava for the fund of a lamp that would light day and night in the chapel of saint Donatus, taking for that a separate document with the strongest insurance, and 1 200 Polish Zloty would be included in the sums disposed below...

⁷ August Jacek Hieronim Plater, c. 1745-1803.

⁸ Referring to Count Konstanty Ludwik Plater.